

PECULIAR ASPECTS OF TRADE RELATIONS OF THE FERGANA VALLEY IN THE 20S-30S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

F.I.Kayumova

Fergana State University

Teacher of the Department of History of Uzbekistan

fqayumova1983@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10404480>

Annotation: This article was created one of the difficult and important periods in the history of our country, including the 20-30s, corresponds to the years of Soviet power. Economic life during the period of Soviet power, the life of the people, culture, history of economic life and its economic significance.

Key words and phrases: Soviet power, private ownership, New economic policy, Military Communism policy, credit cooperation, exchange, property-money relations

Throughout the rich history of the republic of Uzbekistan complex, intricate had experienced their period. Such complex and important period in the history of our country to one of the years of soviet power comes on. The soviet period in the economic life of colonial living disrupted by the fall of the rest of the people, the culture, study the history of economic life, the essence is to understand the importance of independence. The importance of his upbringing in the form of feelings of patriotism especially the youth about the importance of great service.

The soviet power has established total control over the installation of the twentieth century in all areas of life 30-50 years in our history, and particularly in this period of economic life, economic colonization complications in trade relations, business and private entrepreneurship in today's market economy is the study of the history which defines the main directions of development of the society is one of the pressing problems of the period, of course.

So, Uzbekistan's densest population of the fergana valley, which is the development of economic relations in the history of the region is based on the particular form of this process will just like that to learn as a separate survey for the show. Also, the history of the economic relations trade of the fergana valley of Turkistan learn more and more thoughtful xin in income plays an important role.

Of Turkistan, particularly in the fergana valley and the economy of the first world war and October revolution was a great famine vayrongarchilik dissimilar arising as a result of experiencing the condition. The fall of 1917 agriculture will become more severe due to the pessimism of the harvest. All you need is whole grain pud 52 million at this time in the land have grown. Nevertheless, it needs to be grain pud has amounted to 111 million. Destruction by passing the industry also was the departure of the reduction of industrial production from russia and the industry is increasingly reduced as a result of growing food products to bring qimmatilik go without interruption. Mode private ownership of bolshevistik to lose a total of of leadership to the national economy at the same time, the economic method, but not by

way of command directed to sharpen doing administrative work vayrongarchilikni qa famine economic policy.

In 1918 the soviet government in the year of emergency economic measures, conduct demonstrates, this "policy of military communism" of history with the name entered. Whirlwind pulled to hunger than to provide food for the people who sirtan this policy as shown on looks. In fact, except between the rural market the product directly to the city of exchange with this policy, but with the way this event is aimed for the implementation of economic and military violence, famine to mubtalo it is not the people in the front, but the revolution "who protect" the main aspect of the red army and within the country, which is the main mode of the working class were the targets of the food supply. "Military communism" policy in the old Marxist way is the reflection of the imagination that proletar the victory of the revolution with the "law of value" lose their own importance, as well as commodity-money relations and the market towards the end of finds, directly I was expressing the opinion that the product occupies their position.

"Military communism" policy results quickly showed itself. The introduction of this policy in the economic system led to the destruction of land formed for centuries. The economic policy of the soviet government forced to review this thing again.

Deep in the process of the implementation of the new economic policy is the manifestation of the conflict. This is clear in the fergana valley was removed to afford. The fergana valley played a significant role in agriculture especially in this period of cooperation. The industry with tens of thousands of individual peasant farms of the peasants, establishing strong economic relations between the material to improve the situation, enterprises should be to provide assistance with the raw materials was necessary. First years in the country, as well as a much wider popular credit cooperative in the fergana valley. In the village at that time was one of the most vulnerable areas to give you a loan. So here's the basic payday lenders trade and capital position.

Other types of cooperation were also popular in the fergana valley. Thus, 1923 877 units in different cooperative here they 155,5 thousand job I was offered.

The transition to the new economic policy in connection with the preparation and sale of agricultural raw materials on a commercial basis began dealing with the organization of the body. Such trade-economic structures of society and the country among matlubot union (Turksoyuz), Turkestan cotton union and there were others. Product ayrboshlashni has implemented within their options using market mechanisms. For example, 1921 XKS Turkestan republic and russia, according to the decree of 19 years turksoyuzga exchange both natural and mixed with other regions, products with money, buying, selling one product from the right to perform exchange want from like to make using the form was given.

Turksoyuz 1922 November-December during the months from fair Nijegorod surp raw 100 thousand meters, 560 yashik utensils, pud 2 500 iron, samovar 569 pieces, 195 yashik window, window, aluminum pud bought 60 bottles.

Deputy chairman of the foreign trade department to the authority of the Turkestan military Turkkomisiya V all calculations associated with the same area as the center, and financial support to operations and uploaded by other tasks. Therefore, trade in the country led by the center works hand in Turkkomissiya balls.

In the initial years of the state of commercial affairs in the country "Sentrokoj", "Sentroperst", "Glavxlopkom", "Turktekstil", "Turkxlopkom like" have conducted prestigious

organizations later, the preparation of raw materials, transportation and sales began cutting it to a system.

The products that the industry was relatively worthless to purchase local agricultural products. Pricing of such “inconsistency” to the street locked the beginning of the peasants bring their traditional values in the rebirth was serious. For example, in 1919 the year of cotton in relation to sales of pud in 1 arshin to 36 pounds or 88 if you can get the money that comes chit iron, 1923, in the year of this money would be to buy 10 pounds or 39 arshingina chit iron.

The majority of poor quality goods sent from the center. As a result of agriculture, state employees must prepare the product for that “matlubot cooperation” explains grown food as precious then when tax is paid in the remaining part of agricultural raw materials themselves, who do not give products worth nothing in return. Rural citizens were forced to take these goods because the pre-contract was signed. By keeping such a way caused 1922 in July, according to the evaluation of the participants of the plenum of the country's capital, “peasant society that can pull products from the organization that is used to matlubot his labor was seen as”.

Commodity-money relations boost trade and ayriboshlash of the classic form of “military komunizm” specific to the limit, was released. 1921 free trade has developed since the year of the engine and quickly into the rest of the economy was impressive. His sog'lomlashuviga 1922–1924 in the year of the reform money has helped to a certain extent. The state put an end to the disorders of the circulation of money, the currency into circulation – “chervon” was removed. As a result, the internal market, to the restoration of purchasing power of the population go. On the market, the fair has been formed in connection with the opening of a network of banks and credit insurance services was founded. In the meantime, the development of the free economy, strengthen the position of the barriers put by the state was to go to business groups. Between them, the “misunderstanding” of conflicts arising as a result of the new economic reform in the coming year and a new siësat the form of commodity-money relations, the capacity has weakened. 20 of the twentieth century-at the beginning of the year the whole industry to boost economic embodied in the fergana valley, crafts, goods and money of agriculture are reflected in the relationship of the front cover. 1924 year since the total volume of the turnover made up of the sum of the product yarimmillion interaction. The number of retail trade enterprises went exceed a thousand. 1924-25 in the year of agriculture, wholesale trade and cooperation in the field of state share of 56 per cent, of the turnover amounted to 44 percent of the total product.

The company was established on the basis of private capital and trade intermediary, the strict ideological artel under control. Of the state with private capital, tenant, property tax and business owners through various relations district was established. Prioritize sinfiy approach but it did not. Private owners often trade business was put completely free of limit activities while a very large amount in taxes. In 1922, in the year of 90 percent of the trade volume was in the hands of private traders are still local. Internal independent foreign policy and national leaders in the government tried to move. In this regard, the Russian government will provide greater resistance to the soviet government in russia. The soviet government not only from the political aspect, but also in the realm held serious economic prints by some of the artificial barriers stand. Nevertheless, in the valley of the west and the east I was trying to establish trade relations with independent countries. 1922 July 29, RSFSR in the contract concluded

with the government of the country in the valley in the new economic trade relations with foreign countries the opportunity to conduct won. Representatives of the Russian trade office in moscow of the soviet system steadily fully active in addressing the issues of export and import work.

The purchase of the Russian company, which decrease the price of cotton to be sent by local government officials to raise the price of cotton with the purchase of the peasants and on this basis in order to increase the income of the cotton trade, free trade, that is, on the basis of the new economic policy are required to maintain trade.

The soviet system, the country fully steadily, finland, sweden, Germany, turkey, afghanistan, tried to the conduct of trade and economic relations with countries like iran. Also there is a decent contribution in this connection it should be noted that in the fergana valley. But, 1922th July 29, RSFSR in article 6 of the contract with the Russian government trade relations with foreign countries only with the permission of the particular set of can only have been registered. Although he won in the land launched to foreign savdoaloqalarini hence, these relations would be directly controlled by russia.

We can conclude that due to the new economic policy of the transformations that took place one of the important results of the population mainly in the food product is provided with a noticeable twist. Free economic stationery, commodity-money relations and the restoration of proliferation is a bit of a business, although shaving. Shifts in the social condition of the population of the city also was removed to afford. But, the purchasing power of the rural population was much lower.

Economic although he won to put the set of relations, these relations would be directly controlled by Russia.

I can conclude that due to the new economic policy of the transformations that took place one of the important results of the population mainly in the food product is provided with a noticeable twist. Free economic stationery, commodity-money relations and the restoration of proliferation is a bit of a business, although shaving. Shifts in the social condition of the population of the city also was removed to afford. But, the purchasing power of the rural population is much lowerligicha the rest of it was.

References:

1. Цыпкина М. Развитие Промысловой Кооперации Узбекистана. Автореф. Дисс. Канд. Ист. Наук. – Т., 1953.
2. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/12/1). Übungtypologie Im Deutschunterricht. International Scientific And Practical Conference" The Time Of Scientific Progress", 114-119
- 3.
4. Мустабид Тузумнинг Ўзбекистоннинг Миллий Бойликларини Талаш Сиёсати: Тарих Шоҳидлиги Ва Сабоқлари (1865-1990). – Тошкент. 2001.
5. Вахабов М. Формирование Узбекской Социалистической Нации. – Ташкент, 1961.
6. Саидов Ш. Хоразм Халқ Совет Республикасининг Финляндия Билан Савдо Алоқалари Тарихидан (1920–1924 Йй.) // Ўзбекитон Тарихи. 2003. № 2.
7. Каюмова, Ф., & Тешабоева, Г. (2022). По Источниковедению И Историографии Кокандского Ханства. Актуальные Проблемы Истории Узбекистана, 1(1), 277-286.

8. Inomjonovna, Q. F. (2023). Sharq Renessansi Adam Mets Talqinida. Barqarorlik Va Yetakchi Tadqiqotlar Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnali, 3(4), 53-56.
9. Feruzakhon, K. (2022). Formation Of Trade Relations In The Fergana Valley (1920-1925). Procedia Of Social Sciences And Humanities, 4, 30-32.
10. Қаямова, Ф., & Абдухамидова, Э. (2022). Янги Иқтисодий Сиёсат Ва Унинг Ўзига Хос Хусусиятлари. Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnali, 2(10), 49-55
11. Qayumova, F. (2023). Farg'ona Oblastining Xx-Asr Boshlaridagi Ahvoli Va Yangi Iqtisodiy Siyosat Oqibatları. Евразийский Журнал Технологий И Инноваций, 1(4), 194-198.
12. Inomjonovna, K. F. (2023). The State Of Trade And Industry Of The Fergana Valley (1941-1945): Economics Science. Ethiopian International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research, 10(08), 113-117.